

Effect of Baa Detox Herbal Supplement, Cold Water Hip Bath & Chlorophyll Juice with Yogic Adjuvant Therapy in Peptic Ulcer

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Abstract:- Peptic Ulcer affects the world's 10% of the population, and is the main cause of H.pylori. Many treatment options are available at present but there are multiple side effects are also observed. Abdominal Pain, weight loss, indigestion, vomiting, chest pain, and abdominal burning are widespread problems in peptic ulcers. So due to multiple side effects, people are moving forward with yogic therapy with herbal supplements. Many research studies show that yoga therapy with herbal supplements has good results for peptic ulcer patients. The present paper is based on yoga therapy - Pawan muktasana series 1,2,3, with sheetkari pranayama, Nadi shodhan, Kapalbhathi , Vibhaga , surya namaskar , Shavasana and Om Chanting helps to cure peptic ulcer. Here the peptic ulcer is treated with a BAA detox supplement (herbal complexes) which is a Novel product of the study. A cold compressed pack should be used by dipping cotton cloth in cold water which cools in the freezer and applied to the abdomen. A total of 25 patients with different health issues with peptic ulcers were treated in this study. From that, all are cured within 10-30 follow-up days. Results are positive with yoga therapy and herbal supplement- BAA detox herbal supplement. There are no side effects observed in the patient at the end of the study.

Keywords:- Yoga Therapy; Herbal Supplement; BAA- Detox Herbal Powder; Cold-Water Hip Bath; Helicobacter Pylori Peptic Ulcer (H. Pylori); Chlorophyll Powder.

I. INTRODUCTION

Peptic ulcers are lesions in the lining of the stomach, lower oesophagus, or small intestine. Stomach acid erosion and inflammation caused by Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori), H. pylori causes an inflammatory response in the mucosal layer, which attracts neutrophils, lymphocytes, plasma cells, and macrophages, which causes damage and kills epithelial cells. The most typical signs of peptic ulcer disease (PUD) include mild to severe burning abdominal pain that radiates from the navel to the chest. Changes in appetite, nausea, bloody or dark feces, unexplained weight loss, indigestion, vomiting, and chest pain are among the other symptoms [1]. Gastric ulcers and Duodenal ulcers are the main types included in Peptic Ulcers. According to the research, there was one case of PUD per 1000 person-years in the general

population worldwide. One percent of H pylori infections result in PUD each year [2]. The primary risk factors for peptic ulcers include H. pylori infection, alcohol and cigarette use, use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), and Zollinger-Ellison syndrome. Interleukin 1 beta (IL1B) polymorphisms, according to genetic research, change the synthesis of interleukin 1 in the mucosa, causing gastroduodenal diseases associated with H. pylori. Hypochlorhydria or Hyperchlorhydria are observed during the H. Pylori infection during peptic ulcer. H. pylori can also directly affect the H+/K+ ATPase subunit, stimulate somatostatin-linked sensory neurons that produce calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP), or prevent gastrin production. The main mediators of H. pylori infection are cytokines that block parietal cell secretion [3–4]. Treatment choices come in many various forms, such as Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPIs), H2 Receptor Blockers, Antacids, Potassium-Competitive Acid Blockers, Cytoprotective Agents, and medication administered in line with the selected treatment option, such as Omeprazole, Esomeprazole, Pantoprazole, Cimetidine, Aluminium hydroxide, Vonoprazan, Misoprostol Sucralfate, etc. Headache, abdominal discomfort, diarrhoea, nausea, vomiting, constipation, flatulence, vitamin B12 deficiency, osteoporosis, anxiety, depression, dizziness, and cardiovascular events are the adverse effects that have been associated with all therapies frequently. The adverse effects of these medications, according to studies, may include severe side effects such as thrombocytopenia, hypophosphatemia, chalky taste, cramping in the abdomen, electrolyte imbalance, nasopharyngitis, upper respiratory tract inflammation, dermatitis, etc [4]. First-line treatment and second-line treatment for ulcer complications are different therapeutic approaches for treating peptic ulcers. The Japanese Society of Gastroenterology (JSGE) includes clinical case studies that illustrate the adverse consequences of various peptic ulcer disease therapies [5]. One of the treatments for PPD diagnosis is endoscopy. However, there are other adverse effects as well, including as bleeding, infection, gastrointestinal tract tears, and a reaction to sedation or anaesthesia [9]

All of the preceding research on PUD patients shows that there are no longer any unwanted effects when using yoga and herbal remedies. Studies have demonstrated that yoga can be utilized as a non-pharmaceutical therapy or as

an adjunct to pharmacological therapy to treat or even cure chronic epidemic disorders. Yoga's fundamental practices include asanas (postures), pranayama (breath control), pratyahara (withdrawal of the senses), dharana (concentration), dhyana (meditation), and samadhi (absorption) [6]. Yoga reduces the digestive tract's stress response, which has led some to speculate that it may be used to treat GERD and peptic ulcers [7]. It was discovered that practising yoga while taking a herbal supplement was more effective. Due to their pharmacological properties and lack of adverse effects, herbal (natural product) treatments are the most practical. Boiling is a typical method for preparing herbal medicines as tonics, which helps preserve their active ingredients and reduces the risk of unwanted effects [8].

The current study was centred on the treatment of peptic ulcers using yoga (Figure mention below), a unique product called BAA detox, a hip bath in cold water, and chlorophyll juice. At the conclusion of the treatment, excellent results were observed. BAA detox which eliminates all toxins and harmful bacteria fest (Nisoth property) and can entre blood and detoxify the whole blood (Majith property), induces sound sleep due to carminative (vayu nashak), and clear all blood vessels from cholesterol. Applying a cotton cloth dipped in cold water that has cooled in the freezer to the belly will act as a cold compression pack. BAA detox supplements (Figure 1) are herbal complexes that are a novel product of this study that aid in the early and effective treatment of sickness without the presence of any adverse effects. chlorophyll contains a powerful version of one of nature's most potent nutrients. Similar to haemoglobin in the blood, chlorophyll has a number of health advantages that improve cellular health and functioning in the body. It naturally contributes to maintaining your body in the best possible health, getting your body ready to be free of pollutants, unaffected by pollution and stress, and defending against free radical damage throughout the day. Regular use of Unicity premium super chlorophyll helps the body produce more energy and improve overall wellbeing [10-11]. Chlorophyll powder figure 2 mention below.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS AND TREATMENT PLAN

The total 20 no. of patients concluded in this paper. Males and Females with the age of up to 20 are taken for treatment of peptic ulcer. The patients has different types of health issues given in table no.2. From the investigation 60% of patient has constipation, Nausea, vomiting, Indigestion, Acid Eruption, Blenching with scoring grade 3 according to mention in Table no.2. Table no. 1 shown Daily routine of Treatment plan of peptic Ulcer.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table no. 2 Shown the Results of before and after Grade score according to Table no.1. Treatment plan.

According to Table no. 2 results shows positive after the treatment plan. Disease grading score were decreased and no side effect were observed end of the treatment. Follow up days are different for each patient according to there severity.

While yoga may be beneficial in a number of areas, more research is nearly always required to definitely demonstrate these benefits. Yoga may have the potential to be used as a helpful supportive or adjunct treatment that is reasonably cost-effective, may be practised in part as a self-care behavioural treatment, provides a lifelong behavioural skill, enhances self-efficacy and self-confidence, and is frequently associated with other beneficial side effects. Consequently, it is strongly advised that larger, more thorough studies with superior methodological quality and suitable control interventions be conducted [12].

Using plants and herbs as medicine is a very widespread practise that should be incorporated into daily living. It is important to stimulate the use of natural remedies in various health treatments and to include the active principles of plants into contemporary health-care procedures. Herbs are used to relieve irritability and reduce inflammation. Herbs can be applied physically as plasters and liniments or taken internally as pills, syrups, and infusions. The lower socioeconomic classes in society will benefit from the increased accessibility, affordability, and safety of medicine as a result. Future research on the medicinal efficacy of ayurvedic herbs should be conducted in developing nations like India to see whether they may be used alone or in conjunction with western therapy [13].

IV. CONCLUSION

From all above the results and research it can be concluded that BAA detox herbal powder with chlorophyll powder and yoga treatments are more effective treatment for peptic ulcer disease. Yoga therapy - Pawan muktasana series 1,2,3, with sheetkari pranayama, sheetali pranayama, Nadi shodhan, Kapalbhathi , Vibhaga , surya namaskar , Shavasana and Om Chanting are help to cure disease. Herbal supplement are more power than the other marketed allopathy medicine for peptic ulcer. Cold- water hip bath treatment helps in pain and burning on abdominal in peptic ulcer patient. So all above the condition this study shows positive end of the study

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Narayanan M, Reddy K, MD & Marsicano E. Peptic Ulcer Disease and Helicobacter pylori infection, Missouri Medicine. May/June 2018 | 115:3 | 219.
- [2]. Tuerk E, Doss S, Polsley K. Peptic Ulcer Disease. Volume 50, Issue 3, September 2023, Pages 351-362.
- [3]. Kuna L, Jakab J, Smolic R, Raguz-Lucic N, Vce A and Smolic M. Peptic Ulcer Disease: A Brief Review of Conventional Therapy and Herbal Treatment Options. J. Clin. Med. 2019, 8, 179; doi:10.3390/jcm8020179.
- [4]. Wei-Ping Bi, Hui-Bin Man, Mao-Qiang Man. Efficacy and safety of herbal medicines in treating gastric ulcer: A review. December 7, 2014|Volume 20|Issue 45|
- [5]. Kamada T, Satoh K, Itoh T, Ito M, Iwamoto J, Okimoto T, Kanno T, Sugimoto M, Chiba T, Nomura S, Mieda M, Hiraishi H, Yoshino J, Takagi A, Watanabe S, Koike K. Evidence-based clinical practice guidelines for peptic ulcer disease 2020. J Gastroenterol (2021) 56:303–322 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00535-021-01769-0>.
- [6]. Sahni, Singh K, Sharma N, Garg R. Yoga an effective strategy for self management of stress-related problems and wellbeing during COVID19 lockdown: A crosssectional study. PLOS ONE | <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0245214> February 10, 2021
- [7]. Kaswala D, Shah S, Mishra A, Patel H, Patel N, Sangwan P, Chodos A, Brelvi Z. Can yoga be used to treat gastroesophageal reflux disease? International Journal of Yoga. Vol. 6 Jul_Dec-2013.
- [8]. Firenzuoli F and Gori L. Herbal Medicine Today: Clinical and Research Issues, eCAM 2007;4(S1)37–40, eCAM 2007;4(S1)37–40,doi:10.1093/ecam/nem096.
- [9]. The role of endoscopy in the management of patients with peptic ulcer disease, Volume 71, No. 4 : 2010 gastrointestinal endoscopy 663.
- [10]. V.K. Mishra, R.K. Bacheti and Azamal Husen. Medicinal Uses of Chlorophyll: A Critical Overview. Nova Science Publishers, Inc., Hauppauge, NY 11788 (ISBN 978-1- 62100-015-0), pp.177-196.
- [11]. Martins T, Barros A, Rosa E and Antunes L. Enhancing Health Benefits through Chlorophylls and Chlorophyll-Rich Agro-Food: A Comprehensive Review. Molecules 2023, 28, 5344. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28145344>
- [12]. Bussing A, Michalsen A, Khalsa S, Telles S, and Sherman K. Effects of Yoga on Mental and Physical Health: A Short Summary of Reviews. Hindawi Publishing Corporation Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine Volume 2012, Article ID 165410, 7 pages doi:10.1155/2012/165410
- [13]. Dr.sivakrishnan s. Traditional herbal medicines – a review, ijar november 2018, volume 5, issue 4.

➤ Figure and Table Legends

Fig 1 BAA Detox Herbal Supplement

Fig 2 Chlorophyll Powder

➤ The Picture Shows the Different Yoga Poses used in Peptic Ulcer Treatment

Picture 1 Yoga Poses

Picture 2 Yoga Poses

➤ Tables:

Table 1 Daily Routine of Treatment Plan of Peptic Ulcer.

Time	Treatment Plan
6:00 a.m	Chlorophyll juice 3gm in 300 ml water plastic bottle
6:30 a.m	Cold Water hip bath for 20 minutes with specific Techniques
7:00 a.m - 8:00 a.m	Yogic Practices - Pawan muktasana series 1,2,3, each 3 of 5 round with sheetkari pranayama 5 minutes, sheetali pranayama 5 minutes, Nadi shodhan 5 minutes, Kapalbhati 5 minutes, Vibhaga Pranayama 5 minutes, surya namaskar 5 rounds, Shavasana 5 minutes, 11 times Om Chanting (Figure mention below)
8:00 a.m	250 ml bottle gourd and coriander leaves juice
8:30 a.m	Breakfast of 1. bowl contain Sprouted Green Gram(Moong), Sprouted Chickpea(chana) with Grating Carrot and Tomato, 2. with dish of fruits (apple, papaya, guava) and 3. banana milkshake
Before lunch	Jaggery and Ajwain ladoo (chew for 20 minutes in mouth)
Lunch	Jowar Rotli and seasonal sabji
After lunch	Jaggery and saunf ladoo (chew for 20 minutes)
3:30 P.m	Vitamin C Juice (Vital Z Drink)
6:00 p.m	Cold Abdominal compressed pack for 15 minutes with specific techniques
7:15 p.m	Dinner of plain rice with curry or dal, and khichadi
Before sleep	1 tbsp (=10g) Baa detox herbal supplement with 200 ml plain water
9:30p.m-6:00 a.m	Sleep

Table 2 Results of before and after Grade Score According to Table 1 Treatment Plan

Patient No.	Grade score																Follow-up days
	Indigestion		Lethargy		Nausea		Acid Eruption, Blenching		Heaviness In Abdomen		Anorexia		Constipation		Headache		
	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	
1	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	2	1	1	0	1-20
2	2	1	2	1	1	1	3	2	2	1	1	0	3	2	2	1	21-30
3	1	0	0	0	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	1	0	0	0	1-20
4	2	1	2	1	3	2	2	1	2	1	3	2	2	1	2	1	1-20
5	2	1	3	2	2	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	2	1	3	2	1-20
6	1	0	1	0	3	2	1	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	21-30
7	3	1	2	1	2	1	3	1	3	2	2	1	3	1	2	1	1-20
8	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	1	0	1-20
9	1	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	2	1	3	1	1	0	2	1	1-20
10	1	0	3	2	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	1	0	3	2	21-30
11	1	0	2	1	3	2	1	0	2	1	1	0	0	0	2	1	1-20
12	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	3	2	1	0	2	1	2	1	21-30
13	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	2	1	0	0	2	1	1	0	1-20
14	1	0	2	2	3	2	1	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	2	2	1-20
15	1	0	3	2	2	2	1	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	3	2	21-30
16	1	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	2	2	1	0	1	0	2	0	1-20
17	2	1	1	0	2	1	2	1	3	2	0	0	2	1	1	0	21-30
18	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	1	0	2	2	2	1	1-20
19	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	2	1	1	1	1	0	21-30
20	2	1	2	1	2	0	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	1-20